

ARCHITECTURE

YEREVAN'S GARDENS, PARKS, AND GREEN AREAS: ANALYSING ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN, ENVIRONMENT, AND ISSUES. (YEREVAN'S CIRCULAR PARK)

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Abstract

This study presents a comprehensive analysis and professional assessment of the present state of the Yerevan circular Park, along with suggestions for improvement. It encompasses a historical overview, an evaluation of the park's current condition, and an expert opinion.

Keywords: Yerevan, gardens, parks, environment, architecture, design, landscape, green.

INTRODUCTION

The urban development within our region has undergone significant evolution since the period of the Urartu civilization. This era is well-documented through various publications and historical accounts that detail the intricate planning of cities, construction of walls and fortresses, and establishment of advanced irrigation systems.

Armenia witnessed a surge of urban development during the Soviet era, with several cities including the capital, Yerevan, entering a dynamic phase of growth. This period saw the emergence of a distinct architectural identity for Yerevan, as the city's most significant structures were erected.

In conjunction with urban planning efforts, the establishment of green spaces was also given due consideration, as they are an indispensable aspect of urban development. During Yerevan's prosperous period of construction, numerous buildings were erected each year in accordance with population growth, climatic conditions, and transportation requirements. However, it is worth noting that while the prevailing trends and materials of global urban planning were taken into account, there were several factors that were not fully considered. These included future population growth projections, proper inter-community road placement, the design of green spaces, and the issue of air pollution, among others. Undoubtedly, addressing these limitations warrants a dedicated study, review, and discussion by urban planning specialists and architects well-versed in the intricacies of urban development.

This study will focus on the planning of parks and green spaces in Yerevan, exploring the various planning challenges encountered in their development. Drawing upon historical documentation of their past and present state, as well as local research analyses, this study aims to elucidate design and compositional concerns associated with these green spaces. This study aims to examine whether the green areas in Yerevan have been installed and designed appropriately, or whether they have undergone any changes over the years. Additionally, the study will explore any environmental design changes that have taken place, as well as the architectural and design harmony that exists between these green spaces and their surrounding environment.

GARDENS AND PARKS: DESIGNING FOR BEAUTY AND FUNCTIONALITY

Gardens and parks are among the most beloved and cherished public spaces in our cities and towns. They provide us with a respite from the hustle and bustle of daily life, a place to relax and unwind, and a chance to reconnect with nature. But what goes into the design and planning of these outdoor spaces? What makes them so appealing to so many people? Let's take a closer look.

One of the key elements of garden and park design is functionality. A well-designed garden or park should serve a clear purpose and meet the needs of its users. For example, a public park may need to accommodate a wide range of activities, from picnics and sports to concerts and festivals. In order to do this effectively, the park's layout should be carefully considered, with different zones designated for different activities. Amenities such as benches, picnic tables, and restrooms should be strategically placed for maximum convenience.

Another important aspect of garden and park design is aesthetics. A well-designed garden or park should be visually appealing, with careful attention paid to colour, texture, and form. The use of different plants and materials can create a sense of harmony and balance, while water features such as fountains and ponds can add a sense of tranquillity and serenity. Lighting can also play a key role in the design of a garden or park, allowing it to be enjoyed during the evening hours.

Finally, sustainability is an increasingly important consideration in garden and park design. As we become more conscious /բնական/ of our impact on the environment, designers are looking for ways to create outdoor spaces that are not only beautiful and functional, but also eco-friendly. This might include the use of native plants, rain gardens, and sustainable materials such as recycled plastic and composite decking.

Designing gardens and parks is both an art and a science. By combining functionality, aesthetics, and sustainability, designers can create outdoor spaces that are both beautiful and practical. Whether you're looking for a quiet spot to read a book, a place to play, or a venue for a community event, a well-designed garden

or park can provide a welcome respite from the stresses of everyday life.

PARKS AND GREEN SPACES IN YEREVAN

Certainly, let us now delve into the architectural design discourse of Yerevan's parks to gain a better understanding of the city's urban fabric. While the aforementioned discussion pertained to the installation and necessity of parks, our focus will now shift towards an exploration of the architectural design aspects of these green spaces in Yerevan.

There are now more than three dozen parks in Yerevan. They are: Circular Park, English Park, Children's Park, Shahumyan Park, Yerevan 2800th Anniversary Park, Lovers' Park, Diana Abgar Park, Alexander Tamanyan Park, Komitas Park, Martiros Saryan Park, Moskovyan Park, Park named after Misak Manushyan, Park of Nalbandian-Hanrapetutyan Streets, Park and Pantheon named after Komitas, Park named after Tumanyan, Recreation Zone of Ajapnyak Administrative District, Park named after F. Nansen, Park named after D. Anhaght, Victory park, T. Krpeyan Park, Yerevan Zoo, Children's Railway Park, Family Park, V. Davtyan Park, Nor Arabkir Park, Lyon Park, Shoghakat Park, Davtashen Park, Yuri Bakhshyan Park, Vahan Zatikyan

Park, Motherhood Park, "Malatia" Park, Azatamartikner Park, Tigran Metis Park, Botanical Garden, Myasnikyan-Acharyan Street section. In addition to parks, there are also several other green spaces in Yerevan that may not have the formal status of a park but still serve as popular destinations for leisurely walks.

Our study aims to address compositional issues related to the placement and design of Yerevan's gardens. Specifically, we will explore whether these gardens have been placed in an appropriate environment, or if the adjacent buildings have had an impact on the overall architectural composition of these green spaces.

We would like to present a map that displays almost all of the green areas and parks in Yerevan (fig. 1). In particular, we will analyse the Circular Park located in the heart of the city, where we can observe the distortions that have occurred with the park's design over the years since its construction. It is important to note that these changes occurred after 1990, a period during which the architectural and urban planning environment in Yerevan was in a state of disarray and lacked proper oversight (fig. 2). /սպու ընդհանուրը/

Fig. 1. Green areas and Parks in Yerevan

Fig. 2. Circular Park of Yerevan

The Circular Garden is situated in the Kentron community of Yerevan, surrounding the small center of the city and separated by the ring-shaped Getar River into small and large centers. Starting in front of the "Ayrarat" cinema, the park extends to Moskovyan and Ishakyan streets, bordered by Khanjyan and Yervand Kochar streets. The Saint Grigor Lusavorich Mother Church of Yerevan is also located in this area.

The primary purpose of the park is to improve the city's air quality, create a healthy microclimate, and provide a recreational space for individuals to unwind and rejuvenate. The park is widely regarded as one of the most biodiverse areas in the city, with a plethora of tree species present. The Getar River runs alongside the park, serving as a natural source of irrigation for the lush greenery and contributing to a refreshing and humid microclimate within the park. The park stretches for a total length of 5 kilometers.

The circular garden was initially designed in 1924, but it was not realized until the early 1960s. Prior to the park's construction, the area from the Chess House to

the end of the park was occupied by private residences with fruit trees, which were later demolished in the late 1960s. The park's construction was initiated by the "Yerevan Project" N2 architectural studio, under the direction of Fenix Darbinyan. However, the project underwent several modifications during the construction phase, with the intended area of 1200 hectares being significantly reduced.

Based on the provided image, it is evident that the Circular Garden has undergone a significant number of negative alterations between the years 1990 and 2023. Several cafes and restaurants have been constructed within the park, resulting in a considerable reduction of green spaces. Additionally, a vast portion of the park has been occupied by a newly built sports and spa centre, further compromising its original design. Although there have been efforts to carry out landscaping and remove illegal constructions in the park, it has nevertheless deviated from its initial compositional structure and architectural design environment (fig. 3-6).

REVITALISING YEREVAN'S PUBLIC SPACES: A VISION FOR THE DESIGN AND PLANNING OF GARDENS AND PARKS IN THE CITY.

CONCLUSION

Yerevan, the capital city of Armenia, is known for its rich history, cultural heritage, and stunning architecture. However, when it comes to public green spaces, the city has room for improvement. While there are several parks and gardens scattered throughout the city, many of them are in need of revitalization and better planning.

Firstly, the design of Yerevan's public spaces should prioritise functionality. This means creating spaces that are accessible, safe, and comfortable for all residents. This could include adding more benches and seating areas, ensuring that paths and walkways are even and well-maintained, and providing accessible restrooms and water fountains. Additionally, public

spaces should be designed to accommodate a variety of activities, such as picnics, sports, and cultural events.

Secondly, aesthetics should be a key consideration in the design and planning of Yerevan's public spaces. Yerevan is a city with a rich cultural heritage, and this should be reflected in its public spaces. Designers could incorporate traditional Armenian architecture and design elements into park and garden structures, such as pavilions and archways. The use of native plants and trees would not only add to the city's beauty but also promote sustainability and ecological diversity.

Thirdly, the revitalization of Yerevan's public spaces should involve the community. Residents should have a say in the design and planning of public spaces in their neighbourhoods. Public consultations and community engagement should be used to gather feedback and ideas from residents on how they would like to see their local parks and gardens improved. This would foster a sense of ownership and pride in public

spaces, leading to better upkeep and maintenance in the long term.

Finally, the use of technology and innovation can help transform Yerevan's public spaces into modern, high-tech amenities. Smart benches with built-in charging stations and Wi-Fi could be installed, allowing residents to enjoy the outdoors while staying connected. High-tech lighting systems could be used to enhance the beauty of public spaces while also improving safety and security.

It's true that some parks and gardens in Yerevan have undergone renovations and improvements in recent years, with a focus on bringing them up to international standards in terms of aesthetics, architecture, design, and composition. However, the majority of parks and green spaces in the city are still in poor condition and are in need of attention and maintenance. It's important to prioritise the upkeep and development of these public spaces for the benefit of the city's residents and visitors.

In conclusion, the design and planning of Yerevan's public spaces has the potential to greatly enhance the quality of life for its residents. By prioritising functionality, aesthetics, community engagement, and technology, Yerevan's parks and gardens can become modern, sustainable, and beautiful public spaces that are enjoyed by all.

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